

HarvRESt project, Greener Farming with RES: the Catalan use case

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About 30% of the world's energy is consumed within agri-food systems and about a quarter of the total energy is consumed during the production stage, being responsible for a third of agri-food systems' emissions of greenhouse gases. There is therefore a need to reduce the impact of energy consumption in this sector.

For this purpose, HarvRESt has been launched with the aim of vertically integrating Renewable Energy Sources (RES) into farms by improving the existing knowledge of options for reducing carbon emissions on farms, and by maximising synergies between the integration of RES and sustainable agricultural practices. This will result in a decision support system capable of providing ad-hoc recommendations to both farmers and policy makers that will make it possible to achieve improved production rates on renewable energy as well as food & feed, within agricultural communities.

In order to ensure that the main priority of farmers is preserved, namely the agricultural production rates, while achieving improved environmental impacts and a diversity of incomes for agro communities, i.e. energy exchange and biofuels production, HarvRESt will implement a transdisciplinary and holistic approach based on three main pillars:

1. Social engagement and Innovative business models: This includes not only financial issues but also social sciences and organisational considerations.
2. Agricultural and environmental trade-offs: Addressing the impact of RES technologies on agricultural production, potential trade-offs and synergies of the alternatives to be explored.
3. RES sources and smart energy systems: Addresses the modelling and design of the technological alternatives required to support the uptake and upscaling of RES production.

Supporting these pillars, HarvRESt will address the political and regulatory framework to provide recommendations based on the project outcomes, as well as digital aspects, which will be key to support the early stages of planning and design, implement smart systems at farm level and develop the resulting decision support system of HarvRESt.

To gather valuable information, co-create solutions and validate them, HarvRESt will be fed by real data coming from 4 use cases located in Italy, Denmark, Spain and Norway. Moreover, HarvRESt community will involve 200 Agricultural and energy stakeholders and reach more than 1500 Farms in the project.

The Spanish use case will be conducted in Aragon and Catalunya regions. Focusing on the Catalan use case, the main interest is to collect data from the biorefinery to model the biogas production from agro-residues. Furthermore, the fertilizer potential of the nutrients recovered from the resulting by-product (the digestate), which is currently considered one of the expected trade-offs, will be assessed in order to mitigate RES impacts, increase the circularity in the farm and diversify the farm incomes. The nutrient recovery will improve soil quality, water retention, and conservation. In addition, methane production from recycled CO₂ sources to be used as fuel itself or as an H₂ energy carrier will be analyzed.

Acknowledgments: HarvRESt project is funded by the European Union (ID 101136904).

Website: <https://www.harvrest.eu/>